

Levels of Some Antinutritional Factors in Tempeh Produced From Some Legumes and Jojobas Seeds

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Abstract : Soybean, kidney bean and mung bean, three legumes and jojoba seed is an oil seed, were processed into tempeh, a fermented food. Changes in phytic acid, total phenols and trypsin inhibitor were monitored during the pretreatments (soaking and soaking-dehulling-washing-cooking) and fermentation with *Rhizopus oligosporus*. Soaking reduced total phenol and trypsin inhibitor levels in soybean, kidney bean and mung bean also, phytic acid reduced by soaking in kidney bean and mung bean. Cooking was most effective in reducing the activity in trypsin inhibitor .During fermentation, a slight increase in the level of trypsin inhibitor was noticed in soybean .Phytic acid and total phenols decreased during fermentation in soybean, kidney bean but mung bean didn't form the fermented product tempeh that's because antifungal activity of herein a protein in mung bean, which exerts both chitinase activity and antifungal activity against a variety of fungal species. Solid - state fermentation of jojoba seeds was not effective for reducing their content from cyanogenic glycosides (simmondsin).

Keywords : Antinutritional factors, Cyanocengic glycosides (Simmondsin), Tempeh.

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